

**THE IMPORTANCE OF CHARACTER EDUCATION FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF HOLISTIC PERSONALITY ON STUDENTS -
MULTI-SITES STUDY AT SMK PELITA NUSANTARA 1 AND
MAN 1 SEMARANG, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

The implementation of character education in Indonesia is done by through the *school culture* and the habituation integrated inside the entire school subject, embedded approach. The education on character will benefit if supported by the active acts of all education unit and body. The education on character is the answer that we have all been waiting for. The education on character helps to reform the decreasing quality of morals and behaviors of the younger generation, so they could achieve a more holistic personality. The result obtained is that there are types of management of character education executed through and implemented on integrated education onto all school subjects and the school's vision and mission. There are two obstacles earn implementing the education on character, which are external obstacle that could be solved by holding an MOU between school and university, parents, society, making plans and strategy for character school, socialization and monitoring. While the internal obstacle could be handled by a treatment of routine on the students daily activity.

Keywords: implementation, character education, holistic personality

1. Introduction

The globalisation era that is defined by the many competitions/rivalry that forces all sides on different kinds of expertise to keep developing, because education is the key institutions to build this nation's identity and personality. Education in Indonesia is very complex, because problems occur in almost every aspect of it and without doubt that currently the education around the world is having a significant growth and

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development. The growth and development of education could be seen from the building of education facilities and the availability of a more modern facility and infrastructure. But on the other hand, the decreasing quality of moral goes rampage everywhere, including the inside the education world itself. For that reason the campaign on character education in order to decrease the indecency and deviation on behavior should be done (Mulyasa, 2007: 17)

These types of deviation are changing the social norms and value recognize by all bodies of society to an asocial state that already became a part of the culture or the culture itself. The culture cause by these asocial aspects will be visible from the increasing rate of crimes. With different types of problems like this emerging, all deferent types of media and press begin to report and write about it, even putting it on the headline. The other factor that cause the asocial behaviors are the values that came from outside Indonesia that does not went through filterization and adjustment process beforehand, causing a negative effect on the society. That negative effect when let alone could further destruct the moral of the younger generation, especially students.

The decreasing moral of the nation becomes a blurred portrait in the world of education; this could be observed with the following data: on the year 2010, there are at least 128 case of brawl among students. This number increased sharply to more than 100% on the year 2011, there are 330 cases of student brawls that resulted in the deaths of 82 students and from January through June 2012, 139 case of student brawls occurred resulted in the death of 12 students (student brawl data, 2010: 3). Seeing this case, many groups of people feels that Indonesia is now sick and needs to be cured and treated with a proper implementation of character education. According to Mulyasa (2012: 5) the character education by the means of theoretic education has already exist since islam was first created in this world. The character development in islam are modeled on the prophet Muhammad SAW, he posses a shidiq, tabliq, Amanah, and fatonah characters known for the term STAF.

According to KBBI (2008: 682) character are the forms of behavior, traits and personality that attach to a person resulted by the development of internalization that is used for the base of thinking and behaving that cause a certain characteristic on the person itself. The character of an individual will develop/grow well if placed on the right environment so they receive proper education.

The Indonesian law no. 20 year 2003 regarding the national education system (sisdiknas) had already form function and goals on the national education of inside passage 3 that stated : the national education functioned to develop the ability and form a more intellect and dignified behavior and quality of the civilization for a better living standard, helps to increase the development and potential of the students so they could become a faithful children to the god, noble, healthy, wise, vocal, independent, and a responsible democratic citizen (UU Sisdiknas, 2003: 7).

One of our effort to answer the many kinds of problems occurred is to hold and implement character education in schools, because character education nowadays are largely rooted and admitted by the Indonesian citizens, especially the unequal result of different kinds of education when seen from the behavior; moral and norms of a lot of

individual graduating from formal institutions. Because of this fast and proper coaching and directing are needed.

The coaching of a younger generation could be achieved by various effort including the education done organized, gradually, and continuous (Hasan, 2010: 6). The process and result from the education system will not take form/result immediately; it has to go through a process. The development of character education in every education institution is one of the ways to help relieve the decreasing moral and norms of the nation and form individual's personality.

Personality is ways of behaving that has a distinct characteristic of an individual as well as this individual's relationship to the other individual and its environment. According to Majid (2011: 2) an individual's personality could change and develop until a certain level of maturity process which could be achieved by means of education. From this, education for the development of individual could be implemented at schools in hope that the application of this character education in education institutions could help form holistic individual in students. Planning and leading the nation to a better future needs to be done by directing and coaching on the younger generation in order to increase the quality of the Human Resources because the success of a nation are determined by the quality of its human resources, or in other way it could be stated that big nation could be categorized from the quality and character of its people.

This research are done in 2 schools, which are SMK Pelita Nusantara 1 and MAN 1 Semarang, because these 2 institutions could are the top schools favor by the citizen. This could be seen from several indicators such as: 1) accreditation given by education institutions, 2) the amount of person interested, 3) strict and difficult entrance examination, 4) having graduates that posses good characters and quality and others.

Based on this background and reasons, we could see the importance of the education character to shape a holistic personality on students, that is why "the role and importance of character education in developing a holistic personality on students (multi cases study at SMK Pelita Nusantara 1 and MAN 1 Semarang)" are chosen as the title of this research, to state and explain the relentlessness and anxiety of the researcher towards the shaping of a holistic individual through character education at schools

2. Literature Review

2.1 The management of character education in shaping an individual

a. The concept of character education in shaping an individual

Character education could be defined as a system as an effort to educate and put norms and values of good character on individuals of the school including components such as knowledge, conscience, or desire and actions to implement this norms and values to gods, self, each other, environment, as well as the nation so that the individual could become the perfect and balanced human being/ insan Kamil (Samani, 2012: 46). According to Kesuma (2011: 5), character education as a way to educate humans so that they make decisions wisely and practice it into things on daily life, so they could give positive contribution to the society.

According to the understanding above, it could be concluded that character education is a system that puts norms and value of an individual with character to students so that they could practice it into their lives, inside their family, school environment, society and the country so that it brings positive contribution to its environment through a process of transformation on their life's norms and values.

b. The function of character education

The implementation of character education indeed has certain function and benefit. Character education possesses 3 main functions, which are: first, function on development and forming of potential on individual. Character education forms and develops the potential of students so they possess good thinking, heart and behaving according to the philosophical values of Pancasila. Second, function of strengthening an individual's character. Character education separates the nation's culture and filters unsuitable culture of the other nation that is not in line with the culture and character of a dignified nation (Zubaedi, 2011: 5).

c. The management of character education at school

The management of character education depends on whether there is active involvement from the education itself. Character base education by implementing it onto every electives besides the special school subjects/electives that educate characters on individual such as religion classes, history, norms of Pancasila and so on. The implementation of character education at school has to be adjusted to the curriculum and done by the school, as each of them has different characteristics and potential. Every school always has strengths and potential that could be developed according to the commitment in order to embed character education to students, especially at school environment.

2.1 The strategy of implementation of character education on schools

To shape and build character inside the students' personality, the proper function and target could be achieved by the proper strategy applied, that could be done by: a) the implementation of character education by using integrated approach to all subjects of study/electives, b) daily activity and habit that is shaped by the culture at school, c) with socialization on character education helped by or in corporation with all community at school and the society. The effort on shaping character is done by a series of lessons and activities through electives and activities that helps the development of self, done in class and out of class. The habituation on lives, such as: religion, sincerity, discipline, tolerance, hard work, peace loving, and responsibility.

Lickona (1992: 43) states that there are 11 principal aspects in order to effectively implement character base education. The eleven principal elements are (1) develop values of core etiquette and values of performances of its supporters as a foundation. (2) the definition of "character" in a comprehensive way that includes the mind, heart and behavior. (3) use of a comprehensive, intentional and productive approaches. (4) make a school environment full of awareness (5) give students chance to apply moral deeds. (6)

make academic curriculum that is meaningful and challenging that respects all its participators, develop character and helps students to succeed. (7) try to brings out self-motivation from the students. (8) involve the school staff as learning community. (9) grew a sense of togetherness in leadership morals. (10) involve family and bodies of society as partner, and (11) evaluate the school's character, function of school staff as educators of character base education and until where could the students manifests a good character.

In order for character education to work effectively, there are things that has to be done such as: (1) class base design, that are based on relation of teacher as an educator and students as the scholars, (2) school culture base design, that attempted to build a school culture that could shape the student's character with the help of school social institution therefore certain value could be shaped and embedded inside the student's self and (3) community base design.

3. Material and Methods

This research is a qualitative research while the types of research that the researcher's used is a multi-case study. According to Bogdan (1998: 62) multi-study case is a type of research that dig deep into and about a certain social environmental aspect including the individual in it by using two or more background or a data storage space. While the approach used by the researcher is qualitative. According to Moleong (2016: 4) the qualitative research is a research that attempted to unravel the side effect throughly and according to its context through the collection of data from natural background by using self as a key instrument. From the approach of the descriptive qualitative research data produced is that data in the form of speech or writings and observed behavior from the people (object of study) itself. Data analysis in this research is done since before entering the field of research, while at the field of research and after finishing at the research field by the means of data reduction, data display, and *conclusion drawing/verification*. Data analysis in this research started from the formulation and explanation of the problem before getting involved into the field and it goes on until the stage of writing of the research result (Sugiyono, 2009: 245).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Character Education Management in the Students' Formation of Holistic Personalities

The implementation of character education at Pelita Nusantara Vocational School & MAN 1 Semarang is by submitting the 18 character values in all learning materials.

a. Religious character value

The religious character that is applied are : First, before each class begins, the students are asked to pray together, read the names of Allah (*Asmaul Husna*) and recite the verses of Al Quran which are related to the study materials. Second, during the first break, the

teachers encourage the students to perform *salat dhuha*, whilst at the second break; students are expected to perform *salat dzuhur* in congregation. Third, after the class ends, the teacher and the students recite *Hamdalah* together.

b. Honest character value

The implementation of honesty education is carried out inside and outside the classroom. The researcher observed when seeing directly at the honesty canteen, the students bought the items needed themselves then put the money into the box provided. The honesty atmosphere can be felt not only in the honesty canteen, but also in the school cafeteria. There is a large banner with striking letters put on the wall that said: "*God Sees, Angels Take Notes*".

c. Tolerance character value

The implementation of tolerance education is carried out through joint activities such as school competitions or events. The students are taught to not differentiate each other based on their views or beliefs. Furthermore the teachers teach each and every students equally regardless of their ethnicities, races, social economy class and statuses. As well as non-Muslim students, for the Religion subjects, the school respects their beliefs by giving them their own religion teacher accordingly.

d. Disciplinary character value

Disciplinary character education is carried out by instilling the habit of getting in class and submitting assignments on time. Either it is individual or group assignments, students who can submit on time will get better grades, whilst fail to do so will result in reduction of their grades. For punctual and tardy students each has their own notes.

e. Hard work character value

The hard work aspect from character education is implemented in requiring students to work hard in order to meet the minimum completeness criteria (KKM). Especially for PAI subject, the KKM value is 80. The students can not slacking off and need to work hard to achieve that value. In addition to daily tests, midterm tests, end term tests and final tests, there are also individual or structured assignments that must be completed.

f. Creative character value

The creative character value is taught by making videos of the commendable attitudes and etiquettes such as the etiquettes of being a guest in someone else's home, etiquettes of decent attires, and the commendable attitudes whilst being on the street. This is a group assignments consists of 5-7 students. Each has their own role to design scenarios according to the materials given.

g. Independent character value

The implementation of independent character in the classroom is created by giving opportunities for students to work independently. The task can be performed inside or outside the classroom. The deadline is determined by agreement from all students in the class.

h. Democratic character value

The democratic character value is implemented by reaching class decision in unison through discussion. The election of class committee is held in transparency

i. Curiosity character value

The implementation of the curiosity character in the classroom is creating an atmosphere that arouses curiosity. Whilst the curiosity character education is applied by stimulating the students to have thirst for knowledge, especially related to subject matter. In other words, learning experience does not always refer to textbooks and worksheets but also outside the books, so the students have broader knowledge.

j. Nationalism spirit character value

The implementation of the nationalism spirit in the classroom is working together with classmates. While the nationalism spirit character education is cultivated through the spirit of nationalism, love of homeland, having pride in school and alma mater.

k. Love of homeland character value

The character education for love of homeland is implemented by learning PAI subject. When discussing about expansion of Islam in Indonesia, the teacher delivered the subject connected with recent issues in Indonesia. The discussion results are then presented in front of the class.

l. Achievement appreciation character value

The character education for achievement appreciation is implemented by appreciating the students who achieve best scores during tests in the classroom. Furthermore, it is also instilled through habituation. The teachers congratulate students who have best achievements, best grades or participate in championship. For students who have better knowledge in PAI, they are given the opportunity to become Friday Prayer Preacher.

m. Friendly/ communicative character value

The implementation of character education for friendly/ communicative character in the learning process is that the teachers give examples inside the classroom. They try to answer all questions asked by the students in the classroom, but if time is insufficient, the teacher will initiate discussion after class has ended

n. Peace-loving character value

The implementation of character education for the peace-loving character is through understanding the verses from Al Qur'an about democracy, unity and harmony. From those materials, the teacher provides students with an understanding about the importance of peacefulness. More over the teacher also give examples from daily life including problem solving inside the classroom.

o. Character value of love reading

The implementation of character of love reading in class is giving lit of books or writings that students are currently reading. Frequent visits to library, books exchange among fellow students and learning experience that motivates the students to use reference. Another character of love reading education implementation is through book reviews assignments.

p. Environmental awareness character value

The implementation of environmental awareness character is by maintaining the classroom cleanliness, providing trash cans in the classrooms. Habituation of conserving energy by putting on command stickers that said to turn the lights off and close the water taps after being used in each room. Especially for environment conservation matters, the students are expected to take concrete measures as a form of environmental awareness. This proves the students have concerns about the environment.

q. Social awareness character value

The implementation of social awareness value is to emphasize with fellow classmates, carry out social actions, and raising harmony between the citizens as well as in the classroom. Whereas the implementation of social awareness character education is to emphasize with students who absent because of illness, understanding verses of Al Qur'an about orders to help the poor and comprehend the nature of good deeds. Moreover, habituation of symphatize with fellow students or their families who get misfortunes by praying and visiting also by assisting the family needed.

r. Responsibility character value

The implementation of responsibility character value in the classroom is by making scheduled class duties, actively participate in school events and propose problem solving to school issues.

4.2 The Strategies Applied in Overcoming the Character Management Problem in School

The character education implied in Pelita Nusantara Vocational Highschool and MAN 1 Semarang are managed and implemented through integrated learning materials in all subject matters.

a. Character Education Plans

The plan for character education in Pelita Nusantara Vocational Highschool and MAN 1 Semarang were done during the designs of study plans, which is when making syllabus and lesson plans (RPP). There is one column provided for developed character education values. For example, on the syllabus prepared by PAI Teacher for basic reading competition of QS. Ar-Rum: 41, QS Al-A'raf: 56 – 58 and QS Ash-Shad: 27, in the last column after source/ materials/ tools, there is an aspect of character education with values of love reading and thorough.

b. Character Education Implementations

Character education implementations in Pelita Nusantara Vocational Highschool and MAN 1 Semarang are through extracurricular activities, which are by Islam Religious Organization (Rohis) dan reading-writing Al Qur'an. There are 9 programs developed by Rohis for character education implementations which, according to researcher, are very well done, such as independence, curiosity, love reading and social awareness.

c. Character Education Implementations Evaluations

Character education implementations Evaluations in Pelita Nusantara Vocational Highschool and MAN 1 Semarang are applied through work programs in school with full supports from parents with exemplary. Teachers can also set a good example for students. The results from applying these character educations are considered well done with average material values of 90 and the attitudes deserve an A. These character educations proved to have positive impacts on students

5. Conclusion

5.1 Character Education Management in the Students' Formation of Holistic Personalities

Character educations in Pelita Nusantara Vocational Highschool and MAN 1 Semarang are managed through integrated studies in all subject matters and schools' vision & mission. This aims to form students' complete personality so they really can become a whole generation who are religious, polite, all in all a good quality personality by initializing the character values into RPP and encourages students to make good attitudes a habit through religious practices.

5.2 The Strategies Applied in Overcoming the Character Management Problem in School

The strategies used are:

a. Character education obstacles

The obstacles consist of internal and external obstacles.

Internal obstacles come from students, teachers, and headmaster. External obstacles come from the school who has not yet signed MoU with colleges, the questionable leader's personality, stakeholders and citizens around school area

b. Strategies used in overcoming the management obstacles. The strategies used are external and internal strategies

External strategies consist of procuring MOU between the schools and colleges, planning characterized school, socialization, monitoring, cooperation between the school and parents/ guardians, also active roles from the community. Internal strategies consist of doing habitual behaviour of honesty, discipline, hard-working, responsibility, equip students' comprehension about many competences of moral values and urge the students to always perform good deeds.

References

- Ahmadi, Rulam *Memahami Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Malang: Universitas Negeri Malang, 2005.
- Ahmadi, Rulam, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruz Media, 2016.
- B. D. Brooks, and F. G. Goble, *The Case for Character Education: The Role of the School in Teaching Values and Virtues*, Studios 4 Productions, 1998.
- Berkowitz, M. W. and Bier, Melinda, C., *What Works in Character Education: A Research-driven guide for educators*, Washington DC: Univesity of Missouri-St Louis, 2005.
- Bogdan, Robert C. dan Sari Knopp Biklen, *Kualitatif Research for Education: An Introduction to Theory and Metohods*, Boston: Aliyn and Bacon, Inc, 1998.
- Data Tawuran Pelajar, (www.tvonenews.tv/arsip/view/62132/2012/09/27/data_tawuran_pelajar_selama_20102012.tvOn.com), diakses tanggal 15-6-2019, jam 09.20 WIB.
- Hasan, *Pengembangan Pendidikan Budaya dan Karakter Bangsa*, Jakarta: Litbang Puskur, 2010.
- Ivonna, Indah, *Pendidikan Budi Pekerti*, Yogyakarta: Kanisius, 2013.
- Kementerian Pendidikan Nasional, 2010, *Pengembangan Pendidikan Budaya dan Karakter Bangsa*, Jakarta.
- Kementerian Pendidikan Nasional, *Pengembangan Pendidikan Budaya dan Karakter Bangsa Pedoman Sekolah*, Jakarta: Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pusat Kurikulum, 2011.
- Kusuma, Doni, *Pendidikan Karakter Kajian Teori dan Praktik di Sekolah*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2007.
- Lickona, *Educating for Character: How Our Schools Can Teach Respect and Responsibility*, New York: Bantam Books, 1992.
- Majid, Abdul dan Dian Andayani, *Pendidikan Karakter Perspektif Islam*, (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2011.
- Moleong, Lexy J. *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2016.

- Mulyasa, E. *Manajemen Pendidikan Karakter*, Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2012.
- Mulyasa, E. *Standar Kompetensi dan Sertifikasi Guru*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2007.
- Purwanto, Ngalm Ilmu Pendidikan: *Teoritis dan Praktis*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 1997.
- Samani, Muchlas dan Hariyanto, 2011, *Konsep dan Model Pendidikan Karakter*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Satori, Djam'an, dan Aan Komariah, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif* Bandung: Alfabeta, 2010.
- Sekretariat RI, *Undang-undang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional No 20 Tahun 2003*, Bandung: Citra Umbara, 2003.
- Sugiyono, *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2009.
- Sunaryo, *Psikologi untuk Kesehatan*, Jakarta: Buku Kedokteran EGC, 2002.
- Tim Penyusun Kamus Bahasa Indonesia, *Kamus Bahasa Indonesia*, (Jakarta: Pusat Bahasa Departemen Pendidikan Nasional, 2008.
- Trianto, *Pengantar Penelitian Pendidikan bagi Pengembangan Profesi Pendidikan dan Tenaga Kependidikan*, Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media, 2010.
- Wynne, *Character and Academics in the Elementary School*. In J.S. Benigna (ed). *Moral Character and Civic Education in the Elementary School*, New York: Teachers College Press, 1991.
- Zubaedi, *Desain Pendidikan Karakter Konsepsi dan Aplikasinya dalam Lembaga Pendidikan*, Jakarta: Prenada Media Group, 2011.

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